

7th International Conference on Networks and Communications (NCO 2021)

July 24-25, 2021, London, United Kingdom

<https://icaita2021.org/nco/index>

Scope

7th International Conference on Networks and Communications (NCO 2021) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Computer Networks & Data Communications. The conference looks for significant contributions to the Computer Networks & Communications for wired and wireless networks in theoretical and practical aspects. Original papers are invited on Computer Networks, network protocols and wireless networks, data communication technologies, and network security. The aim of the conference is to provide a platform to the researchers and practitioners from both academia as well as industry to meet and share cutting-edge development in the field.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to these topics only.

Topics of Interest

- Big data / Cloud computing and Networks
- Big Data / IoT Analytics in Networking
- Blockchain and Distributed Ledger
- Internet Measurement and Modeling
- Machine Learning and AI in Networking
- Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Virtualization
- Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) and Autonomous cars
- Vehicular Networks & Intelligent Transportation
- VR/AR Streaming
- 5G/6G Cellular Systems and Heterogeneous Networks
- Adhoc and Sensor Networks
- Data and knowledge Representation
- Heterogeneous Wireless Networks
- High Speed Networks
- Information / Content Centric Networks (ICN)
- Internet and Web Applications
- Internet of Things (IoT)
- Measurement & Performance Analysis
- Mobile & Broadband Wireless Internet
- Mobile Networks & Wireless LAN
- Multimedia Networking
- Network Architectures
- Network Based Applications
- Network Operations & Management
- Network Protocols & Wireless Networks
- Network Security
- Networked Systems Applications and Services
- Next Generation Internet

- Next Generation Web Architectures
- Optical Networks and Systems
- Peer to Peer and Overlay Networks
- QoS and Resource Management
- Recent Trends & Developments in Computer Networks
- Routing, Switching and Addressing Techniques
- SDN/NFV and Network Programmability
- Self-Organizing Networks and Networked Systems
- Signal Processing for Communications
- Ubiquitous Networks
- Wireless Communications
- Wireless Multimedia systems

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **April 03, 2021**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **NCO 2021**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issue of the following journals

- [International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications \(IJNSA\)](#) - ERA Indexed
- [International Journal of Computer Networks & Communications \(IJCNC\)](#) - Scopus Indexed, ERA Indexed
- [International Journal of Wireless & Mobile Networks \(IJWMN\)](#) - ERA Indexed
- [International Journal on Applications of Graph Theory in Wireless Ad hoc Networks and Sensor Networks \(GRAPH-HOC\)](#)
- [International Journal of Next-Generation Networks \(IJNGN\)](#)
- [International Journal of UbiComp \(IJU\)](#)
- [International Journal of Ad hoc, Sensor & Ubiquitous Computing \(IJASUC\)](#)
- [Information Technology in Industry \(ITII\)](#)^{New} - ESCI(WOS) Indexed

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : April 03, 2021**
- Authors Notification : May 10, 2021
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : May 28, 2021

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : nco@icaita2021.org or ncoconf@yahoo.com

Submission link: <https://icaita2021.org/submission/index.php>